

ARS COMBINATORIA^{v3.6}
or: The 64 Ways of Order

a Project by Konstantinos Koulaouzidis

Abstract

The driving force behind this project is the search for the possibility to relate and understand seemingly different or dissimilar ideas or disciplines by tracing common patterns and analogies. It is the Pythagoreans who were also open to the idea of achieving this goal with „patterns“ as a possible means: a basic concept on which, according to artists and scientists, not only the sciences are based, but human society and, in the broadest sense, life and the whole cosmic order.

Patterns and numbers are inextricably linked together. 64 very special magic squares are the foundation of the project. They are used in order to correlate numbers, colors, sounds, the binary system (in form of the I Ching) and the base triplets of the essential amino acids.

The long lasting research and combinatorial studies aim to open up dialogues between the realms of science and art, as well as to give a personal artistic interpretation of the aforementioned correlations by means of different forms of presentation.

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A. Introduction

B. Project Background

C. Detailed Project Description

Magic Squares: An Introduction

The Foundation, or: The 64 Squares of the Project

Parallels to the Structure of the Binary System (I Ching)

Parallels to the Structure of the Essential Amino Acids (Genetic Code)

Colors and Sounds

D. Realization and Outlook

The Colors of the Project

Graphic Presentation: 64 Printed Alu-Dibond Boards

The Sounds of the Project

Audiovisual Installation: 1394 Scores for Light and Sound

Symmetric Score Pairs

Symmetric Score Quartets

Theoretical Context: Triolectics, Artistic Research, and Game Theory

Urlaute: Towards a Phoneme Layer

Outlook

E. Appendix

Historical Color-Sound Tables

References

A. Introduction

*"He who understands the numbers (that is: their innermost essence),
understands everything."*

Plato (Timaeus)

The Pythagoreans were convinced that the principles of numbers are the principles of all things in this world. They claimed that "the cosmos is isomorphic with pure mathematics" (Bell)¹ and that everything in the universe can be measured by whole numbers.

For Augustine, numbers also occupy a very special place in the world order. According to him, the numbers were already there before the world came into existence. The abstraction inherent in the figures makes it possible to represent or express almost everything with a clarity that would not be possible with words.

Artists and mathematicians alike have long recognized that numbers play a very important role in art (i.e. golden ratio in design and architecture, number ratios in music scales). On that account the Italian mathematician Luca Pacioli explained 500 years ago: "Without mathematics, there is no art."

At least since Pythagoras there is the belief in a mathematically ordered, harmonious world, a universal theory that explains and connects everything. The vision of a *Harmonia Mundi* or a universal harmony of the spheres again and again derived from proportional correspondences, and was transferred into harmonical systems. In the twentieth century, this was especially the result of Hans Kayser's studies. The belief in a mathematically ordered world has even led Johannes Kepler to some of his discoveries: He had the "unshakably self-evident conviction of a harmony between man, earth, and space ruled by the number – the certainty of a mystical significance of the number" (Hartner)². The Italian Renaissance artist Francesco Giorgio used numerology as some kind of super-discipline in his *Harmonia Mundi* (1525), with the help of which all other disciplines were to be united.

The driving force behind my project is the search for a possibility to relate and understand seemingly different or dissimilar ideas or disciplines by tracing common patterns and analogies. One should also bring to mind Hermann Hesse's "Glass Bead Game" in which the technique of the Glass Bead Game, developed and practiced in fictional Castile, aims at an interdisciplinary integration of art and science. Mathematics and music, and the humanities and natural sciences, drifting apart by advancing specialization, can be reconnected by using the universal sign language of the Glass Bead Game, and can become aware of their common structure.

The Pythagoreans were also open to the idea of achieving this goal by using "patterns" as a possible means: a basic concept on which, according to artists and scientists, not only the sciences are based, but also human society and, in the broadest sense, life and the whole order of the universe.

According to Andreas Goppold³ "the term pattern has gained prominence as key term in understanding mankind's quest to make the universe intelligible, to fashion a Cosmos from the pure Chaos of the indiscriminate swarm of photons, electrons, air pressure changes, chemical and physical stimulants, that organisms are exposed to every instant of their living existence".

1 Endres, Franz Carl, and Schimmel, Annemarie. *Das Mysterium der Zahl, Zahlensymbolik im Kulturvergleich*. (2001): 24.

2 Ibid., (2001): 38.

3 Goppold, Andreas. "Music, Pattern, and the Neuro-Structures of Time." *Noologie – Die Quer-Denker-Webseite*. 4 Oct. 2017. <<http://www.noologie.de/symbol18.htm>>.

Patterns and numbers are inextricably linked together. This "inevitability" of patterns in the universe⁴ suggests that there must be descriptions for all of them. In order to find them, we need a catalog or a list of all possible patterns. This catalog is called mathematics.

B. Project Background

*"Everything is ordered by measure, number and weight,
and the laws are without change."*

Old Testament (Wisdom 11:20)

I've always been interested in and fascinated by numbers, colors, sounds and patterns. At a young age I was already looking for organizing structures that could relate everything with everything. Many scientists and artists have practiced that before me – however their attempts were often based on intuition, esoterism, etc.

As a scientifically-minded person, I wanted to create my own logical system based on existing principles. My idea was that if I managed to detect a system that perfectly and harmoniously arranged elements, I could project colors and sounds on it. And this arrangement of colors and sounds would then likewise be perfect and harmonious.

Some time ago, numbers with interesting, even fascinating features attracted my attention – the so-called "Magic Squares" of the fifth order (5x5), whose numbers exhibit a perfect inherent harmony. I used 64 special squares as the foundation of the project in order to correlate colors with sounds.

Furthermore, I discovered other relevant principles. The number 64, the project's central number, occurs both in the I Ching (64 hexagrams), as well as in the genetic code (64 base triplets of the essential amino acids). This fact led me to the work of Martin Schönberger⁵ who connects both. The hexagram structure of the I Ching and its connection to the binary system confirmed my (originally intuitively) derived foundation of the project. I thereupon included the binary system, the I Ching and the 64 base triplets of the essential amino acids in my project.

This will be described more detailed in the following sections.

⁴ Barrow, John D.. Impossibility: The Limits of Science and the Science of Limits. (1998): 192.

⁵ Schönberger, Martin. Weltformel I Ging und genetischer Code. Aitrang: Windpferd Verlagsgesellschaft, 2000.

C. Detailed Project Description

"Numbers therefore are endowed with great and sublime virtues. For it is no wonder, seeing there are so many, and so great virtues in naturall things, although of manifest operations, that there should be in numbers much greater, [...] for as much as they are more formal, more perfect, and naturally in the celestials. [...] Again, all things that are, and are made, subsist by, and receive their virtue from numbers. For time consists of number, and all motion, and action, and all things which are subject to time, and motion."

Agrippa of Nettesheim (1486-1535), "De occulta Philosophia"

Magic Squares: An Introduction

A magic square is a $n \times n$ square grid (where n is the number of cells on each side) filled with distinct positive integers in the range $1, 2, 3, \dots, n^2$ such that each cell contains a different integer and the sum of the integers in each row, column and diagonal, is equal. The sum is called the "magic constant" or "magic sum" of the magic square and is calculated by the formula: $M = (n^3+n) / 2$

The number n is called the "order" of a magic square.

All following visual examples will be based on an order 5 magic square with a "magic constant" of 65.

1	15	22	18	9	→ 65
23	19	6	5	12	→ 65
10	2	13	24	16	→ 65
14	21	20	7	3	→ 65
17	8	4	11	25	→ 65

1	15	22	18	9
23	19	6	5	12
10	2	13	24	16
14	21	20	7	3
17	8	4	11	25
↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
65	65	65	65	65

1	15	22	18	9
23	19	6	5	12
10	2	13	24	16
14	21	20	7	3
17	8	4	11	25
↙				↘
65				65

In addition to the above definition, magic squares can also possess other special features. The ones important for this project are briefly discussed below.

PanMagic (or Pandiagonal Magic) Squares

PanMagic squares have the additional property that the broken diagonals, i.e. the diagonals that wrap around the edges of the square, also add up to the magic sum. They remain pandiagonally magic not only under rotation or reflection, but also if a row or column is moved from one side of the square to the opposite side.

1	15	22	18	9
23	19	6	5	12
10	2	13	24	16
14	21	20	7	3
17	8	4	11	25

1	15	22	18	9
23	19	6	5	12
10	2	13	24	16
14	21	20	7	3
17	8	4	11	25

1	15	22	18	9
23	19	6	5	12
10	2	13	24	16
14	21	20	7	3
17	8	4	11	25

Symmetric (Regular, Associative) Magic Squares of Odd Order

In a symmetric magic square all numbers symmetrically opposite the center sum to $(n^2 + 1) * 2$. Alternatively, 4 cells symmetrically opposite the center cell plus the center cell add up to the magic sum.

1	15	22	18	9
23	19	6	5	12
10	2	13	24	16
14	21	20	7	3
17	8	4	11	25

1	15	22	18	9
23	19	6	5	12
10	2	13	24	16
14	21	20	7	3
17	8	4	11	25

→ 1+6+20+25 = 52 → 52 + 13 = 65

 → 2+8+18+24 = 52 → 52 + 13 = 65

 → 9+12+14+17 = 52 → 52 + 13 = 65

Ultramagic Squares

Magic squares of the 5th order that possess both features mentioned above (panmagic and symmetric) are called "Ultramagic Squares".

Ultrasupermagic Squares

Code written specifically for this project calculated that there are 1394 combinations of 5 non-repeating numbers, from the first 25 consecutive numbers, that sum to 65. Actually, the 1394 is a subset of the combinations (without repetition) to the k-th class:

$$K(n;k) = (n / k) = (25 / 5) = (25! / 20!5!) = 1,551121e25 / 2,432902e18*120 = 53130$$

or

$$25*24*23*22*21 / 1*2*3*4*5 = 53130$$

An interesting side effect of the 1394 combinations is that some of them have an additional symmetry feature for some order 5 magic squares: 5 numbers forming an exact cross or x (including wrap-around *) also result in the magic sum:

* Wrap-around means when you go off the square at one edge, continue via-à-vis at the corresponding cell.

I call magic squares with all the aforementioned features "ultrasupermagic" and they are the best suited foundation for my project. The perfect harmony inherent in the numbers of these squares (the recurrence of the magic sum) becomes visible when all numbers from 1 to 25 are connected by lines. The graphical patterns that arise are always absolutely symmetrical. They can be looked at in the following section.

The Foundation, or: The 64 Squares of the Project

"...the numbers of the magic square...in this language God had thought before he created the world, and in this language he had said the words around which the world had originated...it remained the memory of the lost unity..."

Marc Petit (Uroboros)

As Mitsumi Suzuki calculated with a self-written computer program there are 16 ultrasupermagic squares. His algorithm went through all possible combinations of the numbers 1-25 (a total of over 15 septillion) and found those to which the rules of ultrasupermagic squares applied.

During my work on this project, it became increasingly important to me that every project-related aspect can be derived visually and with simple patterns. Regarding the 16 ultrasupermagic squares to be used as the foundation of the project, I was looking for an elegant, intuitively accessible solution.

Therefore I was looking for a way to achieve the 16 squares by using visual, logical and combinatorial methods (instead of using a computer program such as Suzuki). Due to the perfect arrangement of the numbers and the symmetrical patterns resulting from their successive connection (see figure on page 13), I was sure that there were underlying principles, and I was eager to find them.

Through reverse engineering (the return of a magic square to its starting square) and other methods I was successful and found out the principles: Certain numbers are never exchanged (marked black in figure below), particular others are moved along a certain pattern (marked in green and blue) and some exchange positions (marked in red). Another important aspect for deriving all squares is that the rows or columns are symmetrically interchanged (swapped) along the respective middle column or row (for the first USM square no rows or columns needed to be swapped).

As there are 4 symmetrical swaps (1,2,4,5) we get 8 possible swapping combinations: 1,2,4,5 (no swap) / 1,4,2,5 / 2,1,5,4 / 2,5,1,4 / 4,1,5,2 / 4,5,1,2 / 5,2,4,1 / 5,4,2,1 for the rows or columns, and by multiplying both, we get 64 possible mixing combinations of rows and columns and thus 64 ultrasupermagic squares. This is not contrary to the 16 squares calculated by Suzuki, because if you examine the 64 squares more closely, you realize that 16 squares produce the rest by rotation. Through mirroring along one of the diagonals, their number can again be doubled or tripled. Those newly created squares do not generate any new essential combinations for the project of the numbers 1 to 25 inside the 64 squares (for more information on this see page 27).

It should also be mentioned that all possible permutations (without repetition) of the numbers from 1 to 25 give an incredibly large number, that is

$$P(25) = 25! = 15.511.210.043.330.985.984.000.000 \text{ or } 1.551121e+25$$

(over 15 septillion = the number 15 with 24 zeros), a number that is said to be as large as all the stars in the observable universe. Imagine that only 64 of them possess the inherent perfection and harmony needed for this project!

All squares produced from each other by rotation are colored identically and I call them "rotational siblings". Here you can see the first proof that the chosen swapping sequence of rows/columns was perfect, as it produces a symmetric pattern of the similar squares and as there is an underlying order on the sequence of their appearance on the following 8 rows, sorting them by rotation. The second proof can be found in "Parallels to the Structure of the Binary System and I Ching" (page 14).

All symmetrical patterns resulting from the successive connection of the numbers 1 to 25 on each of the 64 ultrasupermagic squares. Here again the patterns of the same colored squares are rotations of each other.

Parallels to the Structure of the Binary System and I Ching

The number 64 also drew my attention to the I Ching, the Chinese Book of Changes. The I Ching consists of 64 six-part combinations (hexagrams). Even Leibniz, who invented the binary system, had discovered parallels between binary code and I Ching – he comments on this in his "Two Letters on the Binary Number System and the Chinese Philosophy"⁶.

I began to use this parallel in order to verify the swapping sequence of the columns and rows (from which the magical squares emerge after applying the "Key", see figure on page 11).

The representation of the I Ching hexagrams or states (which can be understood as binary codes) has helped me to determine the swapping order of the rows and columns – in order to create the ultrasupermagic squares: I discovered that the 64 hexagrams of the I Ching, each consisting of two triplets, can binary-encode the alternations of the columns (1st triplet) and rows (2nd triplet) within a square (a hexagram is being read from bottom to top). See a full list of the 64 ultrasupermagic squares and the corresponding hexagrams on the next page. Again I was looking for a visual explanation to verify and link the swapping sequence with the I Ching triplets, which I found and tried to visualize on the following figure:

All possible combinations of 4 symmetrically interchanged (swapped) Columns or Rows and the parallels of the swapping sequences to the Binary System and I Ching.

				swapping sequences	binary numbers	I Ching triplets	Z	
	1	2	4	5	→ swaps: 0 → 1 2 3 4 5	0 0 0		0
	1	2	4	5	→ swaps: 1 → 1 4 3 2 5	0 0 1		1
	1	2	4	5	→ swaps: 2 → 2 1 3 5 4	0 1 0		2
	1	2	4	5	→ swaps: 3 → 2 5 3 1 4	0 1 1		3
	5	4	2	1	→ swaps: 3 → 4 1 3 5 2	1 0 0		4
	5	4	2	1	→ swaps: 2 → 4 5 3 1 2	1 0 1		5
	5	4	2	1	→ swaps: 1 → 5 2 3 4 1	1 1 0		6
	5	4	2	1	→ swaps: 0 → 5 4 3 2 1	1 1 1		7

switch counterparts*
in order to derive the remaining 4 combinations

* Counterparts are: for the Columns & Rows to be swapped [1, 5][2, 4], for the Binary Numbers [0, 1], for the I Ching [--, —]

6 See: Schönberger, Martin. Weltformel I Ging und genetischer Code. Aitrang: Windpferd Verlagsgesellschaft, (2000): 48-50.

The 64 ultrasupermagic squares and the corresponding hexagrams of the I Ching.

Parallels to the Structure of the Essential Amino Acids (Genetic Code)

As this is currently only part of the graphic presentation of the project, for now I am only showing a table with the corresponding Square Number > I Ching Hexagram > Binary Code > Nucleotide Triplet (Codon) > Amino Acid. You can see the full list on the next page.

The translation of a codon into a hexagram is based upon the following rule:

The Watson-Crick base pairs in RNA molecules (e.g., transfer RNA), guanine-cytosine (G-C) and adenine-uracil (A-U), are mapped to the hexagram as in the following figure.

For further details please consult Martin Schönberger's book (see "References" > "Print Media").

For identical amino acids the same color was used. Amino acids having the same biochemical properties (nonpolar / polar, basic / acidic) are colored with similar colors, according to a custom color palette created by taking those properties into account.

Colors and Sounds

*"The primordial nature of color is a dreamlike sound,
Is music turned light."*

Itten (The Art of Color)

Everything in our world is vibration or energy and can be reduced to waveforms or could even be seen as sound. Or as light or even color. Much has already been written and speculated about the relationship between sounds and colors. Just think of the phenomenon of synaesthesia and of the many artists who incorporated the subject in their work (Wagner, Kandinsky, Schönberg, Skrjabin etc.).

Baudelaire, for example, wrote in the "Revue Européenne" (April 1861) about Richard Wagner and Tannhäuser: "...for it would be truly surprising if the tone could not produce the color, if the colors could not produce a melodic motif, and if the tone and the color were not suitable for transmitting thought; especially since things have always been expressed by mutual analogy since the day when God created the world as a complex and indivisible totality."⁷

Tables were designed that matched the sounds with their respective colors. But none of them was scientifically justified, all based more or less on the personal instincts or perceptions (intuitions) of the persons who created them⁸.

Kandinsky, who was convinced that the phenomenon of "color-listening" actually existed and probably possessed this ability himself, assumed the immediate "touch of the soul". Again and again he was bothered by the analogies of color tones and sound colors, which he tried to assign systematically. Thus he connected the basic colors with certain instruments⁹. For him the color is the key, the eye is the hammer and the soul the piano with many strings ("Concerning the Spiritual in Art").

The initial idea was that if you could manage to arrange numbers so that they are perfectly harmonious with each other, you would have the base, even the key, to create a harmonious connection between sounds and colors. I found this key in the "Magical Square" figures explained above.

In the next section the different realizations of the project and the colors and sounds I have chosen will be discussed in detail.

⁷ Maur, Karin v.. Vom Klang der Bilder. (1999): 12.

⁸ For more see appendix under "Historical Color-Sound Tables".

⁹ Maur, Karin v.. Vom Klang der Bilder. (1999): 30.

D. Realization and Outlook

The Colors of the Project

Color can be mathematically defined by the electromagnetic wavelength to which it corresponds. Tests with a spectrometer bring the following results regarding the human perception of color:

	← UV (Ultraviolet)			(Infrared) IR →		
Color	Violet	Blue	Green	Yellow	Orange	Red
Nanometer (nm)	390-450	450-492	492-577	577-597	597-622	622-780

As every human eye is different, and light conditions, reflections and other factors can alter the way one perceives color, the calculated, chosen and printed colors can only be an approximation.

For this project I decided to use the color table below. It was generated by Dan Bruton's FORTRAN program¹⁰. The program calculated approximate RGB values from the wavelengths between 380-780 nm of the light spectrum. I divided the table into pixels so that each pixel corresponds to a nanometer. Furthermore, I decided to use a part of the color spectrum said to be visible for man (about 390-760 nm) and also included the very faint visible parts of the ultraviolet and infrared portion, which are drifting towards black (because not really visible). This finally gives us the scope from 380-760 nm which I divided into 25 equal parts. At the end it was no longer a problem to extract the corresponding RGB values from this table.

In order to produce colors as accurate as possible for the 64 print plates of the project (see next chapter) I used a calibrated screen and a spectrometer. There were quite a few test prints and adjustments of the printing profiles, but I finally achieved a very satisfying result!

¹⁰ Bruton, Dan. "Spectra Code." Approximate RGB values for Visible Wavelengths - FORTRAN Code. 4 Oct. 2017. <<http://www.physics.sfasu.edu/astro/color/spectra.html>>.

For reference, this is the list/table of the 25 colors used in nm and their equivalent RGB values:

	R	G	B
01: 380,00 nm	0	0	0
02: 395,83 nm	0	0	5
03: 411,67 nm	10	0	25
04: 427,50 nm	30	0	70
05: 443,33 nm	55	0	120
06: 459,17 nm	55	0	190
07: 475,00 nm	0	85	155
08: 490,83 nm	0	125	135
09: 506,67 nm	0	180	140
10: 522,50 nm	0	230	150
11: 538,33 nm	0	255	125
12: 554,17 nm	110	255	0
13: 570,00 nm	230	235	0
14: 585,83 nm	255	155	0
15: 601,67 nm	255	75	0
16: 617,50 nm	255	0	45
17: 633,33 nm	235	0	65
18: 649,17 nm	170	0	50
19: 665,00 nm	110	0	35
20: 680,83 nm	65	0	15
21: 696,67 nm	35	0	5
22: 712,50 nm	20	0	0
23: 728,33 nm	5	0	0
24: 744,17 nm	0	0	0
25: 760,00 nm	0	0	0

Graphic Presentation: 64 Printed Alu-Dibond Boards

For the first time the results of long-term research and combination work were visualized and shown at the Goldberg Studios in Munich. They were exhibited from 23 to 26 July 2015 in the form of 64 graphic panels. This is one of the 64 exhibits.

The numbers of the squares contain a perfect harmony: they form absolutely symmetrical graphical patterns by linking the differently arranged numbers from 1-25 per square. This harmony can be transferred visually and logically to other areas as well. The colors from the uniformly subdivided light spectrum (in 25 parts) that are assigned to the numbers are subject to the displayed pattern and thus create a graphic unit: they too produce an optically perfect harmony. In addition, each panel shows the assignment of the numerical square to the binary system, I Ching, and base triplets with associated amino acids.

The Sounds of the Project

I needed 25 different sounds to assign them to the 25 colors, so after several experiments I decided to use a new general musical concept that differs from traditional musical ratios and is based on the harmony of numbers, that is: A numerical sequence of 25 frequencies based on the rational mean, specifically the "Arithmonic Mean" that embraces the well-known arithmetic and harmonic means, along with the new consonance principles related to sound wave patterns shown in the book "New Numerical Methods". For further details please consult Domingo Gomez Morin's book (see "References" > "Print Media"). According to this concept 25 sounds at the following frequencies can be used for the numbers of 1 to 25:

200 Hz, 400 Hz, 600 Hz, 800 Hz, 1000 Hz, 1200 Hz, 1400 Hz, 1600 Hz, 1800 Hz,
2000 Hz, 2200 Hz, 2400 Hz, 2600 Hz, 2800 Hz, 3000 Hz, 3200 Hz, 3400 Hz, 3600 Hz,
3800 Hz, 4000 Hz, 4200 Hz, 4400 Hz, 4600 Hz, 4800 Hz, 5000 Hz

The different settings I used in order to program the instruments and oscillators that create all sounds can be found on each score sheet of the audiovisual installations (see next chapter).

Audiovisual Installation: 1394 Scores for Light and Sound

In the audiovisual installation¹¹ sounds are assigned to the colors from the graphical presentation of the project. If these are played according to certain rules, programmed music compositions (in the style of serial music) originate and harmoniously bring the colors to sound.

Each of the 64 squares (as described in C.) contain 1394 different combinations of 5 numbers from 1 to 25, which always have the sum 65 and are identical for each of the 64 squares. Each combination of numbers forms the basis of a single musical composition or score. Each of the 1394 scores consists of the same 64 subareas (analogous to the 64 squares) and plays 5 different tones per square (analogous to the 5 numbers per square with the sum 65) column by column, plus a silent part equal in length to one tone for the gaps between the squares. For each subarea of a score it is always the same 5 notes, but in different positions (depending on the position of the number in the square). This creates rhythm.

Similar to the twelve-tone technique, no tone is repeated until all 5 have been played, which is anyway the case for each of the 64 squares played. By means of this "five tone technique" each score has a playing time of 96 seconds. This results in a total running time of 37 hours 10 minutes and 24 seconds.

Calculations showed that there are certain groups within the 1394 scores, based on the different unique variations each square in a score plays back. Obviously scores with less unique variations sound very repetitive and the ones with many unique variations sound more diverse.

Color-coded list and overview (map) of all groups:

¹¹ A preview (beta) of the audiovisual installation was exhibited at the Goldberg Gallery in Munich, 13-15.10.2017 and a presentation of the project has been held at the GGR-PY Conference, HfP (TUM), Munich, 14.10.2017.

Symmetric Score Pairs

Further research, concluded in mid-2025 and extended in 2026, revealed an additional layer of structural symmetry within the 1394 scores: every single score has a symmetric partner, forming 697 pairs. Each of the 1394 combinations, viewed as a musical score, that is, a pattern of notes arranged across the 8×8 board of 64 sub-squares, has been paired with a symmetric counterpart. Since pairs always occur within the same variation group, the distribution of pairs across groups mirrors the group sizes: 1 pair (8 unique variations), 20 pairs (16), 16 pairs (20), 4 pairs (25), 170 pairs (32), 46 pairs (56), and 440 pairs (64 unique variations). The pairing involves two distinct symmetry principles:

Single-Square Symmetry: In this type of pair, every individual 5×5 sub-square within the 8×8 board of one score is a rotation or reflection of the corresponding sub-square in its partner score. The symmetry operates locally, at the level of each sub-square independently.

Global Symmetry: In this type of pair, the entire 8×8 board of one score is a rotation or reflection of the board of its partner. Here the symmetry operates at the level of the complete composition, treating the full arrangement of 64 sub-squares as a single entity.

These two principles are independent and orthogonal. A systematic four-way classification of all 697 pairs reveals that they are neither mutually exclusive nor exhaustive: 647 pairs exhibit Single-Square symmetry only, 25 pairs exhibit Global symmetry only, 22 pairs exhibit both types simultaneously, and 3 pairs (all in the group with 25 unique variations: 104/1035, 160/973, 319/878) satisfy neither strict definition, their pairing resting on the combinatorial structure of the group rather than on geometric symmetry of the score patterns.

The research and its results, including an interactive tool for exploring the pair-structures, can be found at www.koulaouzidis.com/ars-combinatoria/research/pairs/.

As an example, let's take the 8 scores of the group with 25 unique variations (the yellow variations on the map) and how they look. Those are the scores with the numbers 104, 160, 319, 432, 759, 878, 973, 1035 and are paired as such: 104/1035, 160/973, 319/878, 432/759. Three of these pairs (104/1035, 160/973, 319/878) are among the three pairs that satisfy neither strict symmetry definition, while 432/759 exhibits Global symmetry. Each score is played from the left column to the right, sounding only the 5 corresponding notes of the score combination (marked in black). Where more than one note is on a column, those will be played simultaneously.

Visualization of Score 319 (Combination: 2, 6, 13, 20, 24)

Visualization of Score 878 (Combination: 4, 10, 13, 16, 22)

Visualization of Score 432 (Combination: 2, 10, 13, 16, 24)

Visualization of Score 759 (Combination: 4, 6, 13, 20, 22)

Visualization of Score 319 (Combination: 2, 6, 13, 20, 24)

Visualization of Score 878 (Combination: 4, 10, 13, 16, 22)

Visualization of Score 432 (Combination: 2, 10, 13, 16, 24)

Visualization of Score 759 (Combination: 4, 6, 13, 20, 22)

Symmetric Score Quartets

Further analysis in early 2026 uncovered a higher-order structure: 198 quartets, groups of exactly 4 scores connected by both symmetry types. Each score in a quartet has two different partners, one via Single-Square symmetry and one via Global symmetry. These four relationships form a closed cycle with alternating symmetry types. Scores connected only by the same symmetry type (the diagonal pairs within each quartet) share no symmetry relationship at all.

The 198 quartets are distributed across four variation groups: 2 in the group with 16 unique variations, 76 in the group with 32, 6 in the group with 56, and 114 in the group with 64 unique variations, accounting for 792 of the 1394 scores. The remaining 596 scores form 298 simple pairs with only one symmetry type, and 6 scores (the three pairs with neither symmetry) stand isolated.

These pair- and quartet-structures show that the symmetry principles inherent in the ultrasupermagic squares are not confined to the numerical level but extend through to the musical scores derived from them. Just as the numbers within each square exhibit perfect balance, the scores, as sonic and visual patterns, mirror each other in structurally precise ways. Harmony and order, once established at the foundational level, are carried through every layer of the system.

An interactive tool for exploring the quartet- and pair-structures, including the four-way symmetry classification, can be found at www.koulaouzidis.com/ars-combinatoria/research/quartets-and-pairs/.

ARS COMBINATORIA
oder: Die 64 Arten der Ordnung

Partitur der Kombination #1 (1, 2, 13, 24, 25)

00 1 15 22 18 9 23 19 6 5 12 10 2 13 24 16 14 21 20 7 3 17 8 4 11 25	01 1 15 24 18 7 23 17 6 5 14 10 4 13 22 16 12 21 20 9 3 19 8 2 11 25	02 2 14 21 18 10 23 20 7 4 11 9 1 13 25 17 15 22 19 6 3 16 8 5 12 24	03 2 14 25 18 6 23 16 7 4 15 9 5 13 21 17 11 22 19 10 3 20 8 1 12 24	04 4 12 21 18 10 23 20 9 2 11 7 1 13 25 19 15 24 17 6 3 16 8 5 14 22	05 4 12 25 18 6 23 16 9 2 15 7 5 13 21 19 11 24 17 10 3 20 8 1 14 22	06 5 11 22 18 9 23 19 10 1 12 6 2 13 24 20 14 25 16 7 3 17 8 4 15 21	07 5 11 24 18 7 23 17 10 1 14 6 4 13 22 20 12 25 16 9 3 19 8 2 15 21
08 1 15 22 8 19 23 9 16 5 12 20 2 13 24 6 14 21 10 17 3 7 18 4 11 25	09 1 15 24 8 17 23 7 16 5 14 20 4 13 22 6 12 21 10 19 3 9 18 2 11 25	10 2 14 21 8 20 23 10 17 4 11 19 1 13 25 7 15 22 9 16 3 6 18 5 12 24	11 2 14 25 8 16 23 6 17 4 15 19 5 13 21 7 11 22 9 20 3 10 18 1 12 24	12 4 12 21 8 20 23 10 19 2 11 17 1 13 25 9 15 24 7 16 3 6 18 5 14 22	13 4 12 25 8 16 23 6 19 2 15 17 5 13 21 9 11 24 7 20 3 10 18 1 14 22	14 5 11 22 8 19 23 9 20 1 12 16 2 13 24 10 14 25 6 17 3 7 18 4 15 21	15 5 11 24 8 17 23 7 20 1 14 16 4 13 22 10 12 25 6 19 3 9 18 2 15 21
16 6 15 17 23 4 18 24 1 10 12 5 7 13 19 21 14 16 25 2 8 22 3 9 11 20	17 6 15 19 23 2 18 22 1 10 14 5 9 13 17 21 12 16 25 4 8 24 3 7 11 20	18 7 14 16 23 5 18 25 2 9 11 4 6 13 20 22 15 17 24 1 8 21 3 10 12 19	19 7 14 20 23 1 18 21 2 9 15 4 10 13 16 22 11 17 24 5 8 25 3 6 12 19	20 9 12 16 23 5 18 25 4 7 11 2 6 13 20 24 15 19 22 1 8 21 3 10 14 17	21 9 12 20 23 1 18 21 4 7 15 2 10 13 16 24 11 19 22 5 8 25 3 6 14 17	22 10 11 17 23 4 18 24 5 6 12 1 7 13 19 25 14 20 21 2 8 22 3 9 15 16	23 10 11 19 23 2 18 22 5 6 14 1 9 13 17 25 12 20 21 4 8 24 3 7 15 16
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32 16 15 7 23 4 8 24 1 20 12 5 17 13 9 21 14 6 25 2 18 22 3 19 11 10	33 16 15 9 23 2 8 22 1 20 14 5 19 13 7 21 12 6 25 4 18 24 3 17 11 10	34 17 14 6 23 5 8 25 2 19 11 4 16 13 10 22 15 7 24 1 18 21 3 20 12 9	35 17 14 10 23 1 8 21 2 19 15 4 20 13 6 22 11 7 24 5 18 25 3 16 12 9	36 19 12 6 23 5 8 25 4 17 11 2 16 13 10 24 15 9 22 1 18 21 3 20 14 7	37 19 12 10 23 1 8 21 4 17 15 2 20 13 6 24 11 9 22 5 18 25 3 16 14 7	38 20 11 7 23 4 8 24 5 16 12 1 17 13 9 25 14 10 21 2 18 22 3 19 15 6	39 20 11 9 23 2 8 22 5 16 14 1 19 13 7 25 12 10 21 4 18 24 3 17 15 6
40 16 15 7 3 24 8 4 21 20 12 25 17 13 9 1 14 6 5 22 18 2 23 19 11 10	41 16 15 9 3 22 8 2 21 20 14 25 19 13 7 1 12 6 5 24 18 4 23 17 11 10	42 17 14 6 3 25 8 5 22 19 11 24 16 13 10 2 15 7 4 21 18 1 23 20 12 9	43 17 14 10 3 21 8 1 22 19 15 24 20 13 6 2 11 7 4 25 18 5 23 16 12 9	44 19 12 6 3 25 8 5 24 17 11 22 16 13 10 4 15 9 2 21 18 1 23 20 14 7	45 19 12 10 3 21 8 1 24 17 15 22 20 13 6 4 11 9 2 25 18 5 23 16 14 7	46 20 11 7 3 24 8 4 25 16 12 21 17 13 9 5 14 10 1 22 18 2 23 19 15 6	47 20 11 9 3 22 8 2 25 16 14 21 19 13 7 5 12 10 1 24 18 4 23 17 15 6
48 21 15 2 18 9 3 19 6 25 12 10 22 13 4 16 14 1 20 7 23 17 8 24 11 5	49 21 15 4 18 7 3 17 6 25 14 10 24 13 2 16 12 1 20 9 23 19 8 22 11 5	50 22 14 1 18 10 3 20 7 24 11 9 21 13 5 17 15 2 19 6 23 16 8 25 12 4	51 22 14 5 18 6 3 16 7 24 15 9 25 13 1 17 11 2 19 10 23 20 8 21 12 4	52 24 12 1 18 10 3 20 9 22 11 7 21 13 5 19 15 4 17 6 23 16 8 25 14 2	53 24 12 5 18 6 3 16 9 22 15 7 25 13 1 19 11 4 17 10 23 20 8 21 14 2	54 25 11 2 18 9 3 19 10 21 12 6 22 13 4 20 14 5 16 7 23 17 8 24 15 1	55 25 11 4 18 7 3 17 10 21 14 6 24 13 2 20 12 5 16 9 23 8 22 15 1 5
56 21 15 2 8 19 3 9 16 25 12 20 22 13 4 6 14 1 10 17 23 7 18 24 11 5	57 21 15 4 8 17 3 7 16 25 14 20 24 13 2 6 12 1 10 19 23 9 18 22 11 5	58 22 14 1 8 20 3 10 17 24 11 19 21 13 5 7 15 2 9 16 23 6 18 25 12 4	59 22 14 5 8 16 3 6 17 24 15 19 25 13 1 7 11 2 9 20 23 10 18 21 12 4	60 24 12 1 8 20 3 10 19 22 11 17 21 13 5 9 15 4 7 16 23 6 18 25 14 2	61 24 12 5 8 16 3 6 19 22 15 17 25 13 1 9 11 4 7 20 23 10 18 21 14 2	62 25 11 2 8 19 3 9 20 21 12 16 22 13 4 10 14 5 6 17 23 7 18 24 15 1	63 25 11 4 8 17 3 7 20 21 14 16 24 13 2 10 12 5 6 19 23 9 18 22 15 1

Wiedergaberelevante Informationen:

Framework für die Programmierung der Oszillatoren: **tone.js Release 8** | <https://github.com/Tonejs/Tone.js>
System mit bester Soundwiedergabe via tone.js: **OS | Windows 10 64Bit, Browser | Chrome Version 54.0.2840.99 m**

Einstellungen für tone.js: Instrument: **Tone.PolySynth** polyphony: 5 Source: **Tone.Oscillator** type: fatsine Component: **Tone.Envelope** attack: 0.0 decay: 0.5 sustain: 0.1 release: 2.4 attackCurve: "linear" releaseCurve: "exponential" Event: **Tone.Loop** interval: 0.25

Finally, one could ask why I wasn't playing the squares produced from mirroring across both diagonals as well. As I am showing in the following figure they do not produce any new musical scores, even if played back by rows instead of columns. Therefore the initially chosen 64 squares without the 2 ways of mirroring are enough for my project.

As an example we are using the first ultrasupermagic square "00" with its 3 rotational siblings "28", "35", "63", seen on the first row. On the second and third row you find the squares produced when the ones on the first row are mirrored across the two respective diagonals. Musical scores that sound identical have the same color.

Squares played by Columns

Squares played by Rows

mirroring
diagonals

In addition to the digital audiovisual installation, selected score pairs have been printed on Fine Art Litho Matte paper and framed in matte black wood. These physical prints give the symmetric pair-structures a tangible, collectible presence alongside the 64 Alu-Dibond panels, bridging the visual and sonic dimensions of the project in material form.

Theoretical Context: Trilectics, Artistic Research, and Game Theory

A separate paper, currently in preparation, positions ARS COMBINATORIA at the intersection of three theoretical frameworks: Asger Jorn's trilectics, Anke Haarmann's theory of künstlerische Forschung (artistic research), and Manfred J. Holler's game theory.

Jorn's trilectics, developed in the early 1960s¹², argues that any complementary relationship must always be at least triple and can never be reduced to a binary opposition. He derived this insight partly from the triangular structure of color complementarity, drawing on Philipp Otto Runge's color sphere, and traced it back to Pythagorean principles. ARS COMBINATORIA shares this Pythagorean root and demonstrates a system in which multiple irreducible domains (number, color, sound, binary code, genetic code) coexist in structural correspondence without any one of them being reducible to the others. At the level of the system as a whole, threefold structures recur throughout the project: the I Ching trigrams that encode the row and column swaps, the three-letter codons of the genetic code, and the triangular symmetries within the line patterns of the 64 squares.

A more concrete trilectical structure emerges from the recently completed research on quartets. Of the 1,394 scores, 792 organize into 198 quartets: groups of exactly four scores linked by two independent and qualitatively different symmetry types (Single-Square Symmetry and Global Symmetry) in an interlocking four-cycle. Within each quartet, every anchor score stands in two irreducible complementary relationships at the same time, one through Single-Square Symmetry and one through Global Symmetry, while these two partners share no symmetry with each other. This mirrors Jorn's color model directly: just as red has its complement through one principle and participates in a different complementary relationship through another, each anchor score participates in two incommensurable symmetry relationships at once. The three scores (the anchor and its two partners) coexist without resolving into a synthesis, which is exactly Jorn's core claim. This threefold relationship is made audible and visible in the animation sequences, where each quartet produces two loops, A-B-A-C and D-B-D-C, each centered on one anchor alternating between its two incommensurable partners¹³. The diagonal scores within each quartet (A and D, B and C) carry no symmetry relationship at all. Their non-relation is not a third symmetry type but the structural shadow of two irreducible principles acting on the same material.

The pair-level observation, that the 697 pairs organize into two irreducible symmetry types coexisting without merging, applies to the full system. The quartet-level argument deepens this for 792 of the scores, showing trilectics not only as a feature of the system's overall architecture but as a property of individual scores within it.

Haarmann asks how art can function as a genuine mode of knowledge production¹⁴. Her central argument is that the methodology of artistic research must be worked out inductively from within artistic practice itself, not imposed from external disciplines. ARS COMBINATORIA is a case in point: the Key, the swapping principles, and the pair-structures were all discovered through sustained visual, combinatorial, and auditory exploration over three decades. The method is inseparable from the work.

A related example can be found in the work of John Coltrane. In 1961, Coltrane drew a diagram, now known as the "Circle of Tones", that maps the twelve chromatic tones geometrically and organizes the

12 Jorn, Asger. *Naturens Orden*. Silkeborg, 1962.

Also: „Open Creation and Its Enemies“, *Internationale Situationniste* Nr. 5, Dezember 1960.

13 Each quartet contains four scores A, B, C, D, where A and B as well as C and D are linked by Single-Square Symmetry, while A and C as well as B and D are linked by Global Symmetry. The animation loops alternate between these two symmetry relationships from the perspective of each anchor score and can be viewed at www.koulaouzidis.com/ars-combinatoria/research/quartets-and-pairs/.

14 Haarmann, Anke. *Artistic Research: Eine epistemologische Ästhetik*. Bielefeld: transcript Verlag, 2019.

tonal space into groups of three (augmented triads). This diagram was not an academic exercise: it was sketched between two sets during a live performance, deriving tonal order from geometry directly out of continued improvisatory practice¹⁵. Despite the fundamental differences between Coltrane's twelve-tone chromatic system and the 25-frequency system used in this project, both share a core principle: the derivation of musical order from mathematical-geometric properties rather than from subjective perception or convention. Coltrane's three-note groupings are also readable as triolectical structures in Jörn's sense, and his practice-based mode of discovery aligns with what Haarmann calls *Produktionsästhetik*: knowledge emerging from the act of making.

Holler's game theory provides a further lens¹⁶. The exhaustive enumeration of all possible states within a rule-based system resonates with the combinatorial analysis central to game theory. The 1,394 scores represent the complete set of possible "moves" within the rules of the system, and their organization into 198 quartets, 298 simple pairs, and 3 pairs with neither symmetry type forms a kind of equilibrium landscape: not Nash equilibria in the classical sense, but structures in which two independent symmetry principles coexist without resolution. The quartet structure in particular, where a score's relational position changes depending on which symmetry principle is applied, can itself be read as a game-theoretic configuration, since each score has different partners and different roles depending on the rule in play. These connections are explored in detail in the forthcoming paper.

Urtaute: Towards a Phoneme Layer

The project's system correlates numbers with colors and sounds. A natural next step is the question whether other domains can be mapped onto the 25 positions in a similarly principled way.

The original idea was to apply the project's principles to alphabets and writing systems. However, alphabets are culturally specific and vary widely in size (from 22 to over 40 letters). A more universal approach presented itself: instead of letters, one could use phonemes, the basic sounds of spoken language. Phonemes are not tied to any particular alphabet or culture but are rooted in the physiology of the human vocal tract.

Using frequency data from the UCLA Phonological Segment Inventory Database (UPSID, covering 451 languages)¹⁷ and the PHOIBLE database (over 3,000 inventories), I investigated which phonemes are most universally attested across the world's languages. The raw UPSID top-20 consonant ranking includes two dental/alveolar doublets: dental / ɲ / alongside alveolar / n /, and dental / t̪ / alongside alveolar / t /. Most phonologies treat these as variants of the same phoneme category. After pooling them, the effective consonant list arrives at 18 distinct sound categories, each attested in at least 30% of the world's languages.

For the vowels, the seven most frequent in PHOIBLE are / i /, / u /, / a /, / o /, / e /, / ɛ /, and / ɔ /. These seven form a complete symmetric primary vowel space: three heights (close, mid, open) across two positions (front, back), plus central / a /. This is not an arbitrary selection. Dispersion-Focalization Theory, developed by Schwartz et al. (1997)¹⁸, predicts this set as a natural stable configuration: when a language expands beyond five vowels, it almost always fills in the open-mid row (/ ɛ /, / ɔ /) to create a three-height system.

15 See: Lateef, Yusef. *Repository of Scales and Melodic Patterns*. Amherst: Fana Music, 1981.

Also: Hollander, Roel. John Coltrane's Tone Circle <<https://roelworld.eu/blog-saxophone/coltrane-tone-circle/>>.

16 Holler, Manfred J. und Barbara Klose-Ullmann. *Strategic Games on Stage*. Cham: Springer, 2025.

17 Maddieson, Ian. *Patterns of Sounds*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1984.

The UPSID database is accessible at: <<https://linguistics.ucla.edu/people/ladefog/PhonsOfLang.html>>.

18 Schwartz, Jean-Luc, Boë, Louis-Jean, Vallée, Nathalie, and Abry, Christian. The Dispersion-Focalization Theory of vowel systems. *Journal of Phonetics* 25 (1997): 255-286.

The 5-vowel system /i, e, a, o, u/ is the most common worldwide (attested in over a third of all languages), and the 7-vowel set is its predicted extension.

That 18 consonants and 7 vowels sum to exactly 25 is not a forced result but a convergence of independent criteria. Both components are arrived at by their own logic: the consonants through cross-linguistic frequency and phonological pooling, the vowels through acoustic dispersion theory. The fact that they meet at 25 fits the project's recurring experience that principled constraints produce unexpected alignments.

This phoneme layer, which I call "Urlaute" (primal sounds), would add a new dimension to ARS COMBINATORIA. The 1394 scores could then be played not only as tones and colors but also as sequences of human speech sounds, derived from the same mathematical foundation. Each 5-number combination within a score would produce a group of 5 phonemes. With an average of 1.4 vowels per group (compared to 1.0 in a 20+5 split), the resulting sequences would contain enough vowels to approximate natural syllable patterns, producing speech-like textures without carrying any semantic meaning.

This connects to the tradition of concrete poetry as practiced by artists like Ernst Jandl, Eugen Gomringer, and the Wiener Gruppe in the 1950s and 1960s. In concrete poetry, language is treated as material: stripped of its semantic function and organized by visual, sonic, or formal principles. The Urlaute layer would work in a similar way, but with one essential difference: the organizing principle is not artistic intuition but the mathematical structure of the ultrasupermagic squares.

The "words" that emerge are not composed but generated, not arbitrary but determined by the same combinatorial laws that govern the colors and tones of the project. A vocal artist performing these sequences alongside the audiovisual playback of the pair-structures would introduce a human presence into the mathematical system: breath, rhythm, and voice as a new medium for the same underlying order.

Outlook

The next steps will be to concentrate on finalizing different audiovisual installations based on the many combinations of the 1394 scores, as well as exploring the translation of the project's visual structures into three-dimensional form, potentially as sculptural objects produced through 3D printing or other fabrication methods.

The Urlaute phoneme layer described in the previous section is planned as a component of the next exhibition, with the goal of integrating vocal performance into the audiovisual installation.

Furthermore I am very interested in collaboration with other artists as well as scientists and researchers interested in my work and the principles behind it. I am especially looking forward to collaborating with composers in the electronic and experimental music genre, as well as with vocal artists and performers.

In addition, I am still working on an extended integration of the 64 base triplets of the essential amino acids of the genetic code. Further extensions will be presented on my website (www.koulaouzidis.com). Future exhibitions are also planned. Stay tuned!

E. Appendix

Historical Color-Sound Tables

The Russian composer Alexander Scriabin (1872-1915) produced the following table for his symphonic poem "Prometheus – Poem of Fire"

C	Db	D	Eb	E	F	F#	G	Ab	A	Bb	B
Red	Violet	Yellow	Steel	Pale blue	Dark red	Light blue	Orange	Purple	Green	Steel	Pale blue

Berlioz, Debussy and Wagner also had a great interest in music and color and for Rimsky-Korsakov C was white.

The Order of the Rosary founded this table on the theory of "Just Intonation":

C	C#	D	D#	E	F	F#	G	G#	A	A#	B
Yellow green	Green	Green blue	Blue	Blue violet	Violet	Violet red	Dark red	Red	Red orange	Orange	Yellow
256 Hz		288 Hz		320 Hz	341 Hz		192 Hz		213 Hz		240 Hz

In the work "Théorie de l'Association et de l'unité universelle de C. Fourier" (Paris, 1841) by Edouard de Poméry, Charles Fourier mentions the following connection between colors, notes and metals:

C	D	E	F	G	A	B
Violet	Indigo	Azure	Green	Yellow	Orange	Red
Iron	Silver	Tin	Platinum	Lead	Gold	Copper

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